

HYGIENE CONDITIONS OF FOOD AND WATER COMPANIES

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Abstract

This paper examined the hygiene conditions of food and water production companies. The study adopted the systematic review research design. Relevant articles were randomly drawn from high rated search websites. Only papers which met conditions for inclusion were selected for review. Analysis was done qualitatively using findings from the selected articles. Results showed that adherence to standard food hygiene practices and water sanitation was poor in developing countries. Findings also showed that good hygiene and water sanitation practices can protect communities from food-borne illness and waterborne diseases. Consequently, the study recommended that food and water company authorities should establish good communication with its personnel in the factory for continual instructions and monitoring; the management of food and water company should also embark on strategic education and regular training for the staff in order to keep pace with new technology in the food processing and water supply industry; and personnel of food and water company to engage in food control by communicating with their host community to educate people about food hygiene.